

A New Spectrophotometric Method for the Rapid Monitoring of Phenyl Isothiocyanate in Coke-Oven Air and Biological Samples

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Phenyl isothiocyanates (PITC), a potentially hazardous chemical is discharged into the atmosphere through the emissions from the quenching process in coke ovens in steel industries¹. Isothiocyanates find varied uses². They are highly toxic³.

A few methods based on chromatography⁴ and dibutylamine⁵, mercapto-ethanol⁶, thioglycolic acid⁷ and 1,2-naphthoquinone-4-sulphonate⁸ are available for the spectrophotometric determination of PITC, but these methods are less selective and involve prolonged pretreatment prior to the determination.

In this communication, a new simple and selective method based on the alkaline hydrolysis of PITC to aniline, and its subsequent diazotisation and coupling with 1,3,5-trihydroxybenzene to form a water-soluble orange-yellow dye is reported. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of PITC in coke oven air and biological samples.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of the colour system shows maximum absorbance at 490 nm and obeys Beer's law in the range of 0.4–3.2 μg in 25 ml of final solution for PITC. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $6.7 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0002 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The standard and relative standard deviation were found to be 0.02 and $\pm 6.8\%$ respectively, for 7 replicate analysis of PITC solution containing 1.6 μg of PITC in 25 ml solution.

It was found that 1 ml of sodium nitrite and 0.5 ml

of 1,3,5-trihydroxybenzene solution were sufficient for the complete colour reaction. The orange-yellow dye formed was stable for 8 h. In ice bath 2 min time was sufficient for complete diazotisation, and constant absorbance values were obtained at pH 2–4 and no buffer was required to stabilise the colour. The favourable temperature for the coupling reaction was 20–30°.

Many compounds like benzene, naphthalene, phenol, pyridine, aldehydes, etc. which interfere in other method^{5–8}, did not interfere. The tolerance limit (in μg within parenthesis) of different diverse species are: NO_2^- , SO_2^{2-} , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} (5000); CH_3COO^- , PO_4^{3-} (4000); HCO_3^- (2000); formaldehyde, pyridine (1500); benzene, phenol, naphthalene, nitrophenol (1000); I^- , Br^- , F^- , cresol (800); xylene, Mg^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Pb^{2+} (500); Fe^{3+} , As^{3+} (200); aldehydes (100).

The recovery was found to be 95–100% in 5% aqueous ethanol for PITC⁸ and 98–100% in 0.1 M HCl for aniline¹⁰.

The proposed method is sensitive, selective, simple and rapid. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of PITC in coke oven air and biological samples.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer with optically matched silica cells and a Systronics 108 spectrophotometer were used. pH was measured with a Systronics 331 pH meter.

A stock solution of 1 mg ml⁻¹ of PITC (Fluka)

TABLE 1—PITC LEVELS OF NINE SITES OF COKE OVEN

Sampling point	Sampling time	PITC level ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	
		Present method	Reported method**
S ₁	2	0.52	0.50
	4	0.99	0.96
S ₂	2	0.49	0.46
	4	0.92	0.90
S ₃	2	0.53	0.51
	4	1.05	1.00
S ₄	2	0.63	0.60
	4	1.27	1.12
S ₅	2	0.44	0.45
	4	1.06	1.00
S ₆	2	0.69	0.66
	4	1.39	1.22
S ₇	2	0.76	0.73
	4	1.21	1.20
S ₈	2	0.75	0.72
	4	1.50	1.30
S ₉	2	0.87	0.84
	4	1.69	1.58

Mean of 3 replicate analyses. ** Ref. 8.

was prepared in 5% ethanol and a working standard of $5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ was prepared. A 0.1 M solution of 1,3,5-trihydroxybenzene (Loba) in 10% ethanol, a 0.3% (w/v)

sodium nitrite solution, a 5% (w/v) KOH and 0.1 M HCl were prepared.

Procedure : To known amounts of PITC were added 5% KOH (2 ml) and glycerol (1 ml). The mixture was gently heated on a glycerol-bath, the vapour of aniline thus obtained⁸ was drawn into two impingers containing 0.1 M HCl taken as absorbing solution. To an aliquot of sample containing 0–50 μg of PITC, was added sodium nitrite solution (1 ml) and kept in an ice-bath for 2 min. Then 1,3,5-trihydroxybenzene solution (0.5 ml) was added and kept for another 2 min for complete colour development. The solution was made upto 25 ml and the absorbance measured at 490 nm against a reagent blank.

Coke oven air samples were collected⁹ from nine coke quenching sites of different batteries of coke oven plant. The flow rate was kept at $1.5 \text{ m}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$ for maximum collection efficiency. A 5% aqueous ethanolic solution (35 ml) was used as an absorbing solution. An aliquot taken from the first impinger, was acidified with 0.1M HCl and analysed as above (Table 1).

To several biological samples of cystiene, urine and blood¹⁰ which were found to be free of PITC, known amount of PITC was added. The aliquot (2 ml) of the sample was deproteinised¹¹ by adding 1% trichloro-

TABLE 2 – PITC LEVELS IN BIOLOGICAL SAMPLES

Vol. of sample = 2 ml	PITC added	PITC found*(μg)		Recovery%	
		Present method	Reported method**	(A)	(B)
Sample	μg	(A)	(B)		
	10	9.50	9.35	95.0	93.5
	20	19.20	19.00	96.0	95.0
Cystiene	30	28.60	28.40	95.3	94.6
	10	9.84	9.76	98.4	97.6
	20	19.70	19.52	98.5	97.6
Blood/Serum	30	29.52	29.34	97.8	97.8
	10	9.68	9.45	96.8	94.5
	20	19.10	18.90	95.5	94.5
Urine	30	28.60	28.42	95.3	94.7

* Mean of three replicate analyses. ** Ref. 8

acetic acid (3 ml). After 25 min the contents were centrifuged and the supernatant was analysed by the above method. The recovery was found to be from 95–100% (Table 2). The results were compared with the standard method⁸ (Tables 1 and 2).

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